

TEACHING VOWELS IN PROGRAMS AND TEXTBOOKS ON "MOTHER TONGUE"

Ganiyeva Dildora Sagdullayevna

2nd-year PhD student of Samarkand state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8049689>

Abstract. *This article analyzes educational materials on teaching vowel sounds in "Mother tongue" programs and textbooks, problems and solutions of teaching vowel sounds in "Mother tongue" textbooks. This article focuses on the development of methods of formation of literary pronunciation skills in students, as well as the rules of teaching national vowel sounds orthoepically. Also, a partial reaction is given to the opinions of some scientists who conducted scientific research in this direction in the field of methodology.*

Keywords: *phonetics, pronunciation, orthography, vowel and consonant sounds, exercises and tasks.*

In order to speak fluently, concisely and logically in the literary language, the rules of teaching national vowel sounds require a deep knowledge of orthoepic pronunciation norms. In the textbooks of the Soviet era, the teaching of Uzbek vowels was formed on the basis of interpretations of the Russian language, as well as its entire grammar. The dominant ideology in the society did not allow taking into account the rich phonetic possibilities of the Uzbek language. As a result, the pronunciation standards of the Uzbek literary language are still noticeable. When the representatives of some regions give interviews on TV programs, they give the impression that they have not had a school education, they speak in incomprehensible dialects. This situation has a negative impact on the process of formation of the Uzbek literary language, as well as on the full implementation of the provisions of the Law "On the State Language".

One of the most important requirements for mother tongue education at school is to prepare students for expressing their opinions [1; 23-b], the textbook "Mother Tongue" for the 5th grades of secondary schools authored by N. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, A. Sobirov, V. Kadirov and Z. Jorayeva, which is in use today (vowel we will enter into the analysis of the provision of educational materials for teaching sounds.

In the textbook, educational materials for teaching vowel sounds are included in the following topics:

Exercise 333 is given to repeat what was learned in elementary school. His condition is as follows: "Pay attention to the following verse of Babur. Separate the vowels and consonants in it.

It's bad if a good person doesn't see it.

Anyone who is bad is punished."

Before the theoretical information about the teaching of vowels and graphics, the following assignment was given: Assignment. Child, divide the words of the book into syllables and syllables into sounds. Say how many syllables and sounds the words consist of. [3; 119-b]

It is undoubtedly a positive phenomenon that in this textbook, exercises that strengthen theoretical information are given in different ways depending on the students' abilities, various puzzles are effectively used, and proverbs and quick sayings are replaced. Of course, there are many achievements. However, there are still places that need to be filled. For example, the condition of some exercises designed for the student to do independently is difficult and unclear

(exercises 333, 334), some questions and tasks after the exercises are not suitable for the age and ability of the students, as well as, there are cases where the content of one question is repeated in another. [3; 120-b]

Among the educational materials in the textbook, there is information about the pronunciation options of the vowel [o'], which is not found in others. We all know that a single sound, mainly vowels, has a great influence on the fluency and impact of a student's speech. If a speaker cannot pronounce even one sound correctly, his speech is distorted. Taking this into account, in this textbook it is extremely important to pay attention to the issue of the correct pronunciation of the vowel [o'] in the composition of words and their differentiation from each other. It is reasonable to consider this as an achievement of the textbook. But it is clear that recognition and learning and teaching are different phenomena. There are places in the textbook where it is necessary to pay attention to this aspect. For example, on page 139 of the textbook, the following information is given: "The sound o' is narrower in words such as lake, oc, чол, зора, motabar, бори, кори, хо and in words like "roz" and "romol" it is heard more widely, but it is always written the same way. Observations require that more specific examples be given to substantiate the opinions expressed, to form the necessary skills and competencies in this regard.

In all the "Mother Tongue" textbooks created, the existing educational materials for teaching vowel sounds are unique. In all of them, vowels and consonants are described, syllables and accents are discussed, and a system of exercises is presented. The level of teaching vowel sounds is closely connected with the sections of orthography and orthography. It can be seen that the "Mother Tongue" textbooks created in the period of independence are somewhat enriched in terms of theory and practice compared to the previous ones. In particular, the existence of two different pronunciation variants of the vowel [o'] was not recognized at all until the textbook created under the leadership of N. Mahmudov. As a result, because the student does not know this, he confuses the vowels [u] and [o'] in spelling.

Subordinating the teaching of the mother tongue at school to useful purposes, assuming that each learned grammatical concept, information, definition and rules help to develop oral and written speech, increasing attention to practical linguistics (rather than theoretical) requires.

Another important requirement for mother tongue education is the development of students' thinking. [4; 128-b]

Educational materials for teaching vowel sounds in the "Mother Tongue" program based on the state educational standards, developed on the basis of a competency approach, are given as follows.

Table 1

SECTION 4. VOWELS AND CONSONANTS (33 hours, A2+: 4 hours)	
Topic 32. Concepts of oral and written speech.	1
Topics 33, 34. Pronunciation and spelling standards (words with spelling, phonetic basis, morphological basis and historical basis).	2
Topics 35, 36. The task of distinguishing the meaning of speech sounds. Pronunciation and spelling of some vowels. Pronunciation and spelling of vowels U and I.	2
Topics 37, 38. Pronunciation and spelling of vowels A and O, O. Pronunciation and spelling of consecutive vowels.	2

Reinforcement. Pronunciation and spelling standards, analysis of the function of speech sounds to distinguish meaning. Work with text and vocabulary. (A2+: 4 hours)	2
Topics 39, 40. Pronunciation and spelling of some consonants. Pronunciation and spelling of consonants Gg-Kk.	2
<i>Topics 41, 42. Addition of suffixes to words ending with Qq consonant and their spelling. Adding suffixes to words ending with the consonant G and their spelling.</i>	2
Topics 43, 45. B, Pronunciation and spelling of the consonant n that comes before the consonants m. Pronunciation and spelling of the consonant jj (dj). Pronunciation and spelling of the consonants X x and H h.	3
Topics 46, 47. Pronunciation and spelling of the consonant DD and Tt. Pronunciation and spelling of the consonant f f.	2
Topics 48, 49. Pronunciation and function of the letter ng ng. Pronunciation of letters III и and Ч ч and their functions.	2
Reinforcement. Pronunciation and spelling of some consonants. Analysis of the functions of letter combinations. Work on vocabulary.	2
Topics 50, 51. Pronunciation and spelling of double consonants. Pronunciation and spelling of a series of consonants.	2
Topics 52, 54. Increase and decrease of sounds, exchange. Use of parentheses.	3
Topics 55, 56. Joint and its types. Rules of syllable transfer.	2
Topics 57, 58. Accent and its types. Word stress. (A2+: 4 hours)	2
Reinforcement. Pronunciation and spelling of double and continuous consonants, increase and decrease of sounds, exchange; analysis of the use of hyphens, the rules of moving syllables, accentuation. Work with text and vocabulary.	2

If we pay attention to what is given in the program, it does not pay attention to the sounds that need to be studied side by side in one lesson when hours are allocated to the pronunciation and spelling of speech sounds, which are the basis of teaching vowel sounds. For example, topics 35 and 36 are devoted to "The task of distinguishing the meaning of speech sounds", "Pronunciation and spelling of certain vowels", "Pronunciation and spelling of vowels u and i". A good result can be achieved if the teacher teaches the vowels [i] and [e] in one lesson based on pronunciation. Because we encounter almost every day that speakers confuse the vowels [i] and [e] in pronunciation.

In the program, 2 hours are allocated for topics 37 and 38 "pronunciation and spelling of vowels a and o, o", "pronunciation and spelling of consecutive vowels". In our opinion, 2 hours should be devoted to the pronunciation and spelling of the vowel [o']. Because the pronunciation of the vowel [o'] and its impact on spelling is complex and requires special attention.

In the general secondary education system, in the process of teaching vowel sounds, the lack of special attention to the shortcomings related to the pronunciation of students creates a number of shortcomings in the society. Academic lyceums or vocational schools do not eliminate the pronunciation "defects" in the student's speech. It is a pity that problems related to speaking in the literary language and correct pronunciation exist in the speech of a large number of teachers, sometimes also in the speech of teachers of the mother tongue and literature subjects. At a time when learning foreign languages is given special importance, it is necessary for everyone to be able to speak fluently in his mother tongue. After all, it determines the place of a person in society,

the level of culture. The 32nd topic of this textbook includes theoretical information and definition of the concepts of oral and written speech. In our opinion, it is necessary to provide important information about the importance of literary language in the student's life and the role of literary pronunciation in this place of the textbook. Because most textbooks provide information about the definition and forms of the literary language, nothing is said about its great service and importance in the future life of a person. Rather, it is very important that the promotion of the literary language is clear enough to change the mind of the student who speaks the dialect.

2 hours are allocated for the topics "Accent and its types", "Word stress". In advanced classes, this time is 4 hours. We believe that this (taking into account that word stress is a necessary criterion for correct pronunciation) should be aimed at the same 4 hours for all levels.

It is important that the educational materials for teaching vowel sounds, including examples of exercises and assignments, are in a complex form, that is, they complement each other. Along with the correct pronunciation, as mentioned above, the student should develop skills such as spelling literacy, vocabulary enrichment, and logical thinking at the same time.

So, to what extent are our current "Mother Tongue" textbooks able to meet these requirements as the main educational tool of general secondary education? The following analysis is connected with the answer to this question.

Adapting the student's pronunciation to the norms of the literary language is one of the complex issues, and in this process, it is necessary to work with each of the students individually. In different regions of the country, there are problems with the pronunciation of different sounds, syllables, additions, and words. In the exercises in the textbook, in the educational tasks created by the teacher, attention should be paid to the aspects that adapt the pronunciation of the sounds that are difficult for the student to the literary norms. It is known that vowels [u]-[o'], [i]-[e]; There are many errors in pronunciation and writing of consonants [h]- [x], [q], [j], [ng]. Therefore, it is necessary to pay the main attention to the exercises related to the pronunciation of these sounds.

Topics 43, 45 in the current program for the 5th grades from the "Mother tongue" of general secondary schools are the pronunciation and spelling of the consonant n before the consonants b, m. Pronunciation and spelling of the consonant jj (dj). A total of 3 hours were allocated for the pronunciation and spelling of consonants X and H. 2 hours is not enough to work on problems and confusions in the pronunciation and spelling of the last two consonants. In our opinion, there is a need to make the consonants [x] and [h] a separate topic. Because it is possible to constantly observe that students mix these two sounds mainly in pronunciation and spelling.

In the education of the mother tongue, in particular, in the teaching of vowel sounds, the question of the influence of dialect vowels on the literary language vowels is the main problem that needs to be solved. There are 9 different pronunciations of the vowel in the local language. Most of the teachers of the mother tongue do not distinguish it. In fact, the teacher should strictly teach in the literary language. This aspect should be taken into account in the textbooks.

Although important information about the pronunciation and spelling of the vowel [i] is given in the "Mother language" textbooks, some debates are emerging in the teaching process of vowel sounds. In Uzbek, [i] is not pronounced like in Russian. At this point, it is necessary to distinguish between the pronunciation and naming of letters representing sounds.

When analyzing the content of educational materials for teaching vowel sounds in elementary school programs and textbooks, the following was revealed:

In the 1st grade, the topic "Sounds and letters" was given, and a total of 28 hours were allocated to it. For example: Sounds and letters. Vowels and letters; Pronunciation and spelling of vowels a and o, i and u, o and o. Consonants and letters representing them. Pronunciation and spelling of certain consonants (pronunciation and spelling of consonants d-t, b-p, z-s), consonants d, t, which are dropped at the end of the word. Letter combinations: sh, ch, ng. Alphabet: The name of the letters. Uppercase and lowercase letters. Write words in alphabetical order. The importance of the alphabet.

The parentheses (‘), form it correctly in the word structure. The function of the hyphen in the word is to make the preceding vowel sound longer, to separate the previous syllable from the next, and to differentiate the meanings of words.

A syllable. Dividing words into syllables. Syllable transfer, syllable-by-syllable words consisting of one vowel, stop words, consecutive words with the same consonant following the same path moving to the road. The letter combination (sh, ch, ng) is given as the transfer of words from one way to another.

In the 2nd grade, after repeating (6 hours) what was learned in the first grade, 50 hours were devoted to teaching vowel sounds, which covered the following topics:

Vowels and consonants, their difference. Labeling sounds with letters. Vowels and letters. Designation of six vowel sounds in the Uzbek language with six vowel letters. Pronunciation and spelling of the vowels [a] and [o] , [u] and [i] , [e] , [o'] and the consonants explosive f and p, h and x and the sound ng represented by the letter combination. The stop sign (‘) and its use, such as the function of the stop sign in a word.

The following information is provided on the topic "Joint". Move the part of the word that does not fit in the previous line to the next line. A word has as many syllables as there are vowels. The composition of a syllable is made up of a vowel, one vowel and one consonant, and one vowel and several consonants.

Special attention is paid to "joint transfer". Syllable transfer of a word from one path to the next. A single vowel that forms a syllable cannot be left in the previous path or moved to the next path. One-syllable words, (two-syllable words such as mother, ahil, apricot, sieve) are not divided for copying. Splitting 'in for transfer, leaving the stop sign in the front syllable (wa'-da, mash'-al, ta'-lim). si-ngil, ko'-ngil, tong-gi) syllable-by-syllable copying of words with the same consonant that come next to each other (like ik-ki, kat-ta, is-sik) Voiced and unvoiced consonants sounds, their spelling, checking the spelling of such words by adding a vowel sound to the end of the word: (my school is school, my book is book, my goal is my goal, my hope is my hope) Consonants that are dropped in pronunciation. such as friend) included their spelling study materials.

It can be seen that in the 3rd grade, fewer hours are devoted to teaching materials for teaching vowel sounds. For example:

Sounds and letters. Vowels and consonants and letters. Syllables, rules for dividing words into syllables and dividing them into syllables. Analyzing words into syllables, sounds and sounds - letters; The punctuation mark and its use. letter combinations sh, ch, ng, words with the same consonants that appear in a row and their spelling. It consists of the spelling of consonants that come at the end of a word, with voiced and unvoiced pairs.

In the 4th grade, 10 hours have been allocated for the teaching of educational materials for teaching vowel sounds, which are as follows:

Vowels and consonants, their literal expression; pronunciation and spelling of words with vowel sounds that differ in pronunciation and spelling; pronunciation and spelling of voiced and unvoiced consonants; words with the same double consonant and their spelling; such as words with consonants at the end of the word and their spelling, words with x-h sounds and their spelling, pronunciation and spelling of words with a consonant.

In this class, 2 hours are allocated to the topic "Joint". Dividing words into syllables; syllable formation of vowel sounds; moving words from one line to another syllable by syllable; analysis of words in terms of syllables, sounds and letters, as well as reorganizing words in alphabetical order, information about the importance of the alphabet is covered.

When analyzing primary school programs and textbooks, it was found that they also do not have special pronunciation exercises. However, during the period when the student's speech apparatus is being formed, it is necessary to regularly conduct phonetic exercises based on repetition of difficult-to-pronounce speech sounds.

REFERENCES

1. Ғуломов А., Неъматов Ҳ. Она тили таълими мазмуни. –Т.: Ўқитувчи, 1996. – 23-б.
2. Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A., Sobirov A., Qodirov V. Она тили. Umumiy o`rta ta'lim maktablarining 5-sinfi uchun darslik. – Т.: Маънавият, 2015. – 224 б.
3. Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A., Sobirov A., Qodirov V. Она тили. Umumiy o`rta ta'lim maktablarining 5-sinflari uchun darslik –Т.: Ма`naviyat, 2007 –119-б.
4. Ғуломов А., Неъматов Ҳ. Она тили таълими мазмуни. Она тили ўқитувчилари учун қўлланма. – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1995.–128 б.